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DEVELOPMENT OF GREEN TEA AQUEOUS EXTRACT LOADED CHITOSAN MEMBRANE FOR WOUND HEALING AND IT'S EFFECT IN CONTROLLING NOSOCOMIAL INFECTION.

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ABSTRACT

Tissue regeneration supported by biocompatible scaffolds faces delay in regeneration due to *Staphylococcal* attack. This study was conducted to develop a chitosan based tissue regeneration scaffold with antistaphylococcal property. Chitosan membrane loaded with different concentrations of green tea aqueous extracts {0.016mg (GTM 1), 0.02mg (GTM 2), 0.1mg (GTM 3), 0.5mg (GTM 4), 1.0mg (GTM 5), 1.5mg (GTM 6) & 2.0mg (GTM 7) extract/0.86mg membrane} were prepared and morphological properties, degradation and antistaphylococcal activity were examined. Microbial growth inhibition zone diameter in solid agar medium was significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) for GTM-7, when compared to other concentrations. The inhibition of *Staphylococcus aureus* in the presence of GTM 7 was analysed in liquid media and the antibacterial property was evaluated by spread plate and turbidity measurement. This study revealed that chitosan membrane loaded with green tea aqueous extract showed a better activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* and therefore, it can be used as a scaffold for tissue regeneration. Film solubility test performed in PBS, pH 7.4 showed that the solubility of GTM 7 was significantly increased when compared to unloaded chitosan membrane. The scanning electron microscopic image of GTM 7 showed a rough and uneven surface morphology due to the incorporation of green tea components. This study showed a remarkable lethal action against the nosocomial infecting agent during wound healing with the help of green tea aqueous extract loaded chitosan membrane. This will have a good therapeutic significance in fast tissue regeneration.

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INTRODUCTION

Tissue engineering mediated by polymeric scaffolds gains immense importance in the current scenario. Eventhough, an enhancement in cell proliferation is seen in polymeric scaffold supported wound healing over conventional methods, bacterial infection at the wound site may slow down the process of recovery. Our research addresses this problem through the design of a chitosan membrane, conjugated with the antibacterial aqueous extract from green tea leaves.

Chitosan is an important component of the shells of crustaceans. It is an important natural and safer polymeric scaffold. Chitosan is a natural and non-toxic biopolymer produced by the deacetylation of chitin. Chemically chitosan is a poly- β (1, 4)-glucosamine. It is also found in various insects, worms, fungi and mushrooms in varying proportions from species to species [1]. The solubility of chitosan mainly depends on its biological origin, molecular weight and degree of acetylation. Chitosan is recently used in regenerative medicine and skin tissue engineering as a scaffold. Scaffold can serve as a matrix for cell adhesion and regulate certain cells *in vivo* and *in vitro*. Scaffolds are of either synthetic or natural origin. Synthetic scaffolds are polylactic acid, polyglycolic acid, polycarbonates, etc. Natural scaffolds are collagen, gelatine, albumin, fibrin, cellulose, chitosan, agarose, etc [2]. Chitosan improves homeostasis and promote granulation of cells.

Chitosan also shows antibacterial property. Common wound pathogens are *Prevotella melaninogenicus*, *Porphyromonas asaccharolytica*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, *E. coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Antibiotics used against these organisms are Amoxicillin, Cephalexin, Erythromycin, etc. Certain natural antimicrobial agents like extracts of thriphala, *Myrianthus aboreus*, butterfly pea, turmeric, etc are also used in natural medicine [3]. Polyphenolic compounds of green tea shows anti- bacterial property against *S. aureus* and other gram positive and gram negative organisms. *S. aureus* is gram positive bacteria with diameter 0.5-1.5 μm . They are non-motile, non-sporing bacteria. The most *Staphylococcal* infections include impetigo, boils, carbuncles, abscesses and infected wounds. Chitosan biomaterials are largely used to treat full-thickness skin defects resulting from traumas, burns and skin ulcers [4,5]. Chitosan was reported to improve homeostasis [6] and promote granulation by enhancing the function of inflammatory cells such as fibroblasts, leukocytes and macrophages [7]. This chitosan scaffold also improves regeneration of dermis and epidermis [8]. Considering the regenerative property of chitosan and microbial inhibitory activity of green tea polyphenols, a biocompatible polymeric natural chitosan scaffold loaded with green tree active extract was developed and antimicrobial properties were studied. This study aims to open a path for further developments in enhanced wound healing by introducing a two in one scaffold that possess cell proliferation and antistaphylococcal activity.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

CHEMICALS

Acetic acid (Nice chemicals, Edappally, Kochi, India), NaOH (Nice chemicals, India), Chitosan flakes (Pelican biotech, Alappuzha, India), NaCl (Nice chemicals, India), KCl (Nice chemicals, India), Na_2HPO_4 (Nice chemicals, India), KH_2PO_4 (Nice chemicals, India).

CULTURE MEDIA

Peptone broth, Mueller Hinton agar and Nutrient Agar (Hi Media laboratories Pvt. Ltd, Mumbai, India).

PREPARATION OF CHITOSAN MEMBRANE

One gram chitosan was weighed in a beaker and was dissolved using 2% acetic acid solution. Air bubbles were removed by centrifugation. After centrifugation 30ml of solution was poured into a plate without forming any air bubbles and was kept inside the hot air oven for overnight at 60°C. pH of the membrane was neutralised by dipping it in 0.1M NaOH for 2 hours and washed with deionised water for 4 times. Finally, the membrane was kept for drying overnight [9].

PREPARATION OF GREEN TEA AQUEOUS EXTRACT LOADED CHITOSAN MEMBRANE (GTM)

Chitosan membranes of 6mm diameter were loaded with 20 μl aqueous green tea extract having the concentrations of 0.016mg (GTM 1), 0.02mg (GTM 2), 0.1mg (GTM 3), 0.5mg (GTM 4), 1.0mg (GTM 5), 1.5mg (GTM 6) & 2.0mg (GTM 7) extract/0.86mg membrane. Discs were dried at room temperature and sterilised under UV for 30 minutes.

STUDY OF MORPHOLOGY BY SCANNING ELECTRON MICROSCOPE

The morphology of chitosan membrane was examined by scanning electron microscope (JEOL Model JSM-6390LV).

EVALUATION OF ANTI-STAPHYLOCOCCAL ACTIVITY OF GTM

Anti-staphylococcal activity of green tea aqueous extract loaded chitosan membrane was confirmed by both disc diffusion method and bacterial killing assay technique.

ANTI-STAPHYLOCOCCAL ACTIVITY OF GTM USING KIRBY-BAUER DISC DIFFUSION METHOD

Mother culture was prepared by inoculating *S. aureus* (ATCC 25922) from a sub cultured tube and was incubated at 37°C in a test tube for 24 hours. Sterile cotton swab was used to seed the bacterial culture on MHA plates. Unloaded chitosan membrane was used as control disc. Test membranes (GTM 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 & 7) along with the control discs were placed on the surface of the medium by gentle pressing. The plates were incubated at 37°C, overnight and the zone of inhibition was observed. Methicillin disc was used as positive control.

EVALUATION OF ANTI-STAPHYLOCOCCAL ACTIVITY OF GTM BY BACTERIAL KILLING ASSAY.

Mother culture of *Staphylococcus aureus* was prepared and incubated for 24 hrs at 37°C. The mother culture of 100µl was serially diluted with dilution range of 10⁻¹, 10⁻², 10⁻³, 10⁻⁴ & 10⁻⁵. The corresponding test tubes were marked as P1, P2, P3, P4, & P5. Triplicates of each dilution were considered for this study. An NC or negative control (bacteria alone), PC or positive control (bacteria+methicillin disc) and T or test (bacteria+GTM 7) were considered for each dilution. Blanks like peptone water alone, peptone water with methicillin disc and peptone water with GTM 7 were considered to nullify the effect of medium, methicillin and green tea aqueous extract. 200 µl of the broth solutions from each tube was transferred into microtitre plates and the optical density at 665nm was noted. A graph was plotted against bacterial dilution on X-axis and OD on Y-axis. Then the same sets of tubes were incubated for 24hrs at 37°C. After incubation, micro titre plating was performed and OD value was noted for each dilution. OD in the Y axis was plotted against dilution factor in X axis to study the pattern of bacterial killing by GTM 7. This method can be used to estimate the total number of cells after interacting with the bactericidal agents, which includes living cells, dead cells, and noncellular material that absorbs/scatters the light.

100µl of bacterial suspension from P3, P4 & P5 after 24 hours incubation were taken and performed the spread plate on nutrient agar to enumerate the surviving bacteria in the NC, PC, & T of each dilutions. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. Colonies were counted using colony counter and corresponding Colony forming units were calculated.

FILM SOLUBILITY TEST

Dried GTM 7 and plane chitosan membrane (0.1 mg) were placed in two separate glass tubes with 1ml of PBS (pH 7.4) and shaken gently at room temperature for 24 hours. The solution was then filtered through whatmanns No.1 filter paper to recover the remaining undissolved film. The remaining pieces of film were dried at 110°C to get final dry weight. The experiment was repeated to get significant data. Solubility % was calculated by using the following equation:

$$\text{Solubility \%} = \frac{(\text{Initial dry weight} - \text{Final dry weight})}{\text{Initial dry weight}} \times 100$$

STATISTICS

Statistical evaluations were done with analysis of variance (ANOVA), using GraphPad Instat (version 2.04a, San Diego, USA). Student–Newman–Keuls test was used to compare different groups after ANOVA. ANOVA assumes that all the data follow Gaussian distribution and the tests were done by the method of Kolmogorov and Smirnov.

RESULTS

PREPARATION OF CHITOSAN MEMBRANE.

The membrane was thin, transparent and light gold in colour. After loading aqueous green tea extract, the membrane was turned to green colour (Figure:-1 A & B).

Fig 1 - Preparation of chitosan membrane.

Plain chitosan membrane, B- chitosan membrane loaded with plant extract

SCANNING ELECTRON MICROSCOPIC STUDY

The morphology of the samples was analysed by scanning electron microscope (SEM). The unloaded membrane showed smooth surface whereas green tea loaded membrane possessed rough surface (Figure :- 2 A & B).

Fig 2 – Scanning electron microscopic image.

Plain chitosan membrane, B- chitosan membrane loaded with plant extract. Scale bar = 10µm

ANTI-*Staphylococcal* ACTIVITY OF GTM USING KIRBY BAUER DISC DIFFUSION METHOD

Aqueous extract of green tea has anti-bacterial activity against *S. aureus*. Zone of inhibition was observed for GTM 4, GTM 5, GTM 6 & GTM 7. A significant ($P < 0.01$) increase in zone diameter was observed for GTM 7 when compared to GTM 4, 5 & 6. Our results also showed a significant increase ($P < 0.01$) in zone diameter for GTM 6 when compared to GTM 5 and GTM 4. A significant ($P < 0.01$) increase in zone diameter for GTM 5 when compared to GTM 4 (Table-1) & (Figure:- 3 A & B).

Table-1:-Zone diameter obtained for different GTM concentrations against *Staphylococcus aureus*.

SL.NO	MEMBRANES	ZONE DIAMETER(MM)
1	GTM-1	0±0
2	GTM-2	0±0
3	GTM-3	0±0
4	GTM-4	11.6±0.38*
5	GTM-5	14.3±0.3 [#]
6	GTM-6	16.0±0.3 [*]
7	GTM-7	17.6±0.3 [°]

GTM-Green tea aqueous extract loaded chitosan membrane, GTM-1:-0.016mgextract/0.86mg membrane, GTM-2:-0.02mg extract/0.86mg membrane, GTM-3:-0.1mgextract/0.86mg membrane, GTM-4:-0.5mgextract/0.86mgmembrane, GTM-5:-1.0mgextract/0.86mgmembrane, GTM-6:-1.5mgextract/0.86mgmembrane, GTM-7-2.0mgextract/0.86mgmembrane, * ($P < 0.001$) when compared to GTM-3, [#] ($P < 0.001$) when compared to GTM-4, [°] ($P < 0.001$) when compared to GTM-5, [°] ($P < 0.001$) when compared to GTM-6.

Fig 3- Anti-staphylococcal activity of GTM using Kirby Bauer disc diffusion method.

NC- negative control, PC-positive control, GTM-1:-0.016mg extract/0.86mg membrane, GTM-2:-0.02mg extract/0.86mg membrane, GTM-3:-0.1mg extract/0.86mg membrane, GTM-4:-0.5mg extract/0.86mg membrane, GTM-5:-1.0mg extract/0.86mg membrane, GTM-6:-1.5mg extract/0.86mg membrane, GTM-6:-2.0mg extract/0.86mg membrane.

EVALUATION OF ANTI-*Staphylococcal* ACTIVITY OF GTM 7 BY BACTERIAL KILLING ASSAY.

From the disc diffusion study, GTM-7 was showing maximum zone of inhibition and therefore, it was used for bacterial killing assay.

Before incubation, there was no significant change in the OD values of PC, NC and T of P1, P2, P3, P4 and P5 respectively (Figure: 4a).

Fig 4a- Evaluation of anti-staphylococcal activity of GTM 7 by bacterial killing assay at zeroth hour.

NC-Negative control, PC-Positive control, T-Test; *(p<0.05) when compared to NC of each dilutions. *(p<0.05) when compared to NC and PC of each dilutions.

After 24 hour incubation, the bacterial density was significantly decreased in both PC & T, when compared to NC of all cases. In P1, P2, P3, P4 & P5 the OD value of PC was significantly decreased when compared to T (Figure 4b).

Fig 4b - Evaluation of anti-staphylococcal activity of GTM 7 by bacterial killing assay after 24 hour incubation.

OD measured after 24hrs of incubation

NC- Negative control, PC-Positive control, T-Test; *(p<0.05) when compared to NC of each dilutions, #*(p<0.05) when compared to PC of each dilution.

After visualizing the spread plate, the enumeration of *Staphylococcal* colonies in plates corresponding to P1 and P2 were difficult due to the formation of bacterial lawns. In the plates corresponding to NC of P3, P4 & P5 the enumeration was difficult due to too numerous number of closely arranged colonies (Figure: 5).

Fig 5 - Enumeration of live bacteria by spread plate method.

Live colonies in the samples from dilutions 10^{-3} (A), 10^{-4} (B), 10^{-5} (C).

NC- Negative control, PC- Positive control, T- plate with bacteria grown in the presence of GTM-7

DISCUSSION

Chitin and Chitosan, the naturally abundant and renewable polymers have excellent properties such as biodegradability, biocompatibility, non-toxicity and adsorption. Chitosan can also be used as a scaffold, and stimulate the regeneration of tissues. Chitosan improves homeostasis [5] and thereby promote the granulation in regenerating tissues by enhancing the function of inflammatory cells such as leukocytes, fibroblasts and macrophages. Chitosan is a biopolymer that is well known to accelerate the wound healing. It was reported that chitosan stimulated the migration of polymorphonuclear (PMN) as well as mononuclear cells and accelerate the reepithelialisation for normal skin regeneration [9]. Chitosan has antibacterial activity against a broad range of bacteria including gram negative and gram positive bacteria. The amine group of chitosan plays a pivotal role in the antibacterial mechanism of chitosan.

The anti-staphylococcal activity of GTM was studied by disc diffusion method and bacterial killing assay. Catechins in green tea have biological effects which inhibits the organisms [10]. It has been documented that green tea contains catechin and polyphenols which are highly sensitive to the oxidation process. The catechin and polyphenols have been found to possess antibacterial and antiviral action as well as anticarcinogenic and antimutagenic properties. These compounds could be responsible for the inhibition of pathogens. The results of the study showed that the leaf extract of *Camellia sinensis* inhibited the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus*, which is one of the common wound infecting bacteria. Therefore, zone obtained for GTM was exclusively due to the presence of green tea aqueous extract. The zone of inhibition increased with increasing concentrations of green tea aqueous extract in chitosan membrane. The anti-staphylococcal property using black tea and green tea was observed for *S. aureus* and *S. Epidermidis* [10]. Activity against methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) was confirmed by Toda *et al.* in 1990 [11], using a "cup of tea" strength infusion. Researchers found that *S. aureus* (including MRSA) and coagulase-negative *Staphylococci* to be the species most susceptible to green tea. EGCg appears to be chiefly responsible for this direct antibacterial activity, with the aflavins playing a part in tea extracts [12]. Tannins have been reported to be bacteriostatic or bactericidal against *Staphylococcus aureus* [13].

Antistaphylococcal activity was proved by disc diffusion method, but the nature of bacterial killing by GTM-7 in liquid culture was understood by change in optical density of P1, P2, P3, P4 and P5 followed by counting of viable cells by spread plate method. When this membrane as a scaffold was used, it would get contacted with body fluids. This will result in liberation of green tea compounds to the tissue surrounding and degradation of membrane occurs as a part of resorption by the body. Therefore, the antibacterial activity rendered by the methicillin disc and GTM-7 will be different in liquid culture compared to that seen in solid media. Culture density evaluation before and after reacting with GTM-7 showed the effect of green tea aqueous extract against *Staphylococcus aureus* in liquid culture. In turbidity measurement, there was an increased antistaphylococcal activity observed in positive control.

But in spread plate, an increased antistaphylococcal activity was showed by GTM-7. Absorbance / culture density was increased due to the presence of both live and dead cells when compared to spread plate. The spread plate experiment showed a decline in colony forming units as it includes live cells alone. There is a loss in linearity between culture density and absorbance at values greater than 0.8, due to source light reflection by the very large mass of cells. Furthermore, at these cell densities some of the cells will effectively shield others cells from the light. Both reflection and self shading will result in an underestimation of actual cell count. It is important to remember that the turbidity method will only produce a (rough) estimate of viable cells per ml of culture because both living and dead cells were measured.

In both turbidity measurement and spread plate a decline in bacterial growth was obtained in the presence of methicillin. In the case of GTM-7, a suppression of bacterial growth, which was lesser than that of methicillin was observed. The compounds in green tea released into the broth gradually resulted in reducing the bacterial count as incubation proceeds. So an increased turbidity was observed in culture broth with GTM-7 than the broth with methicillin. Eventhough, the biomass (both dead and live cells) was more in the culture with GTM-7 than with methicillin that was observed by optical density measurement, the actual decrease in live bacterial cells were confirmed by spread plate method. The faster activity of methicillin suppressed the bacterial growth in the beginning, leading to decrease in total biomass [14] but as incubation proceeds it was found that certain cells gained resistance and survived when compared to GTM-7 exposure. Bacteria that have acquired resistance mechanisms can grow at a higher antibiotic concentration than the more susceptible wild-type population and are defined as microbiologically resistant [15]. Most of the resistances in the bacteria result from genes that are located on horizontally transferred genetic elements (e.g. plasmids) and a mutator [16]. *Staphylococci* may react to challenge with an antibiotic by producing a thickened cell wall. Further, in *S. aureus* strains with a reduced susceptibility to methicillin, both naturally occurring and those selected in the laboratory, cell wall thickening may play a role in their resistance. Reduced drug accumulation (activation of efflux pump) can also be a reason for resistance [17]. The above evidences supported the better anti staphylococcal property of GTM 7 than methicillin.

Chitosan is well known to possess valuable properties for biomedical applications and being able to enhance the healing of wound. An increase in the water sorption of chitosan was already proved [18]. This was explained by increase in the hydrophilic groups on the chitosan with amine groups. Biodegradable polymers are used to provide temporary support for cell growth, degrading with time, in a controlled way into products, this can be eliminated by regular metabolic pathways in the body (biodegradation). *In vivo*, chitosan gets degraded mainly by the action of lysozyme. The degradation kinetics of chitosan is inversely related to the degree of deacetylation, since this enzyme targets the acetylated residues of chitosan polymer. Human lysozyme is found in several body fluids like serum, tears, saliva, and other fluids those surrounding cartilage. During the inflammation process, neutrophils and macrophage cells release enzymes, such as lysozyme and reactive oxygen species [19]. Succinic acid is the main degradation product, which is an intermediate of the tricarboxylic acid cycle, which ultimately degrades into carbon dioxide and water. Some biomaterials are degraded by hydrolysis and decomposed in contact with water or serum in a non regulated way [20].

In this study, the importance of chitosan biomembrane for wound healing along with the advantage of suppressing nosocomial infection due to *Staphylococcus aureus* was highlighted. In future, this biomembrane can be further utilised for animal based wound healing experiments and thereby direct to clinical study.

CONCLUSION

This work concluded that the green tea loaded chitosan membrane inhibited the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus*. The liberation of green tea was more efficient in broth than solid media because the pores on the surface of chitosan will be wide opened, which will be favourable for the interaction of green tea with bacteria. Chitosan being an acceptable scaffold in wound healing, the conjugation of green tea extract will help to prevent nosocomial infection and thereby enhances scaffold mediated cell proliferation and reduces secondary complications. Thus, green tea aqueous extract loaded chitosan membrane can be commercialised effectively. This study can be further extended by conjugating other biocompatible polymers like starch or gelatin with chitosan and thereby, increasing the integration and absorption of the scaffold by the body to hasten the wound healing.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

GTM - Green tea aqueous extract loaded chitosan membrane

OD – Optical density

PC – Positive control

NC – Negative control

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Declare no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Krajewska B. Chitin and its derivatives as supports for immobilization of Enzymes. *Acta Biotechnol.* 1991; 11: 269-27.
2. Yan H, Xiong H, Hu Y, Wang S, Zhang R, Zhang C. Layered manufacturing of Tissue Engineering Scaffolds via Multi-nozzle Deposition. *Mater Lett.* 2003; 57:2623-28.
3. Jin Y, Ling PX, He YL, Zhang TM. Effects of chitosan and heparin on early extension of burns. *Burns.* 2007; 33:1027-31.
4. Guo R, Xu S, Ma L, Huang A, GAO C. The healing of full-thickness burns treated by using plasmid DNA encoding vegf-165 activated collagen-chitosan dermal equivalents. *Biomaterials.* 2011; 32:1019-31.
5. Kozen BG, Kircher SJ, Henao J, Godinez FS, Johnson AS. An alternative hemostatic dressing: Comparison of celox, hemcon, and quikclot. *Acad Emerg Med.* 2008; 15:74-81.
6. Ueno H, Mori T, Fujinaga T. Topical formulations and wound healing applications of chitosan. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev.* 2001; 52:105-15.
7. Dalia IS, Jaime L, Diana MM, Ana AE and Claudia AV. The use of chitosan as a skin-regeneration agent in burns injuries: A review. *e-Polymers.* 2022; <https://doi.org/10.1515/epoly-2022-0011>
8. Amal B, Veena B, Jayachandran VP, Shilpa J. Preparation and characterisation of Punica granatum pericarp aqueous extract loaded chitosan-collagen-starch membrane: role in wound healing process. *J Mater Sci Mater Med.* 2015; 26(5):181.
9. Feng P, Luo P, Ke C, Qiu H, Wang W, Zhu Y, et al. Chitosan-Based Functional Materials for Skin Wound Repair: Mechanisms and Applications. *Front. Bioeng. Biotechnol.* 2021; <https://doi.org/10.3389/fbioe.2021.650598>.
10. Wu M, Brown AC. Applications of Catechins in the Treatment of Bacterial Infections. *Pathogens.* 2021; 10: (546)1-17
11. Toda M, Okubo S, Ikigai H, Shimamura, T. Antibacterial and anti-hemolysin activities of tea catechins and their structural relatives. *Nihon Saikingaku Zasshi.* 1990; 45: 561-66.
12. Jeon J, Kim JH, Lee CK, Oh CH, Song HJ. The Antimicrobial Activity of (-)-Epigallocatechin-3-Gallate and Green Tea Extracts against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Escherichia coli* Isolated from Skin Wounds. *Ann Dermatol.* 2014; 26(5): 564-69.
13. Dong G, Liu H, Yu X, Zhang X, Lu H, Zhou T, Cao J. Antimicrobial and anti-biofilm activity of tannic acid against *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Nat Prod Res.* 2018; 32(18):2225-28.
14. Kot B, Wierzchowska K, Piechota M, Gruzewska A. Antimicrobial Resistance Patterns in Methicillin-Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* from Patients Hospitalized during 2015-2017 in Hospitals in Poland. *Med Princ Pract.* 2020; 29:61-68.
15. Fair RJ, Tor Y. Antibiotics and bacterial resistance in the 21st century. *Perspect Medicin Chem.* 2014; 28(6): 25-64.
16. Dimitriu T, Matthews AC, Buckling A. Increased copy number couples the evolution of plasmid horizontal transmission and plasmid-encoded antibiotic resistance. *PNAS.* 2021; 118 (31). e2107818118
17. Sutton JAF, Carnell OT, Lafage L, Gray J, Biboy J, et al. *Staphylococcus aureus* cell wall structure and dynamics during host-pathogen interaction. *PLOS Pathogens.* 2021; 17(3): e1009468. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.ppat.1009468>
18. Correlo VM, Pinho ED, Pashkuleva I, Bhattacharya M, Neves NM, Reis RL. Water absorption and degradation characteristics of chitosan-based polyesters and hydroxyapatite composites. *Macromol Biosci.* 2007; 7(3):354-63.
19. Mittal M, Siddiqui MR, Tran K, Reddy SP, Malik AB. Reactive oxygen species in inflammation and tissue injury. *Antioxid Redox Signal.* 2014; 20(7):1126-67.
20. Lyu S, Untereker D. Degradability of polymers for implantable biomedical devices. *International journal of molecular sciences.* 2009; 10(9): 4033-65.

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